

TERRA VISION

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services
to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

D14.1

Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation
strategy and Market uptake (initial version)

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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
D&C	Dissemination and Communication
D	Deliverable
T	Task
TG	Target Group
GA	Grant Agreement
EU	European Union
CRM	Critical Raw Material
DIH	Digital Innovation Hub
EO	Earth Observation
DoA	Description of the Action
KER	Key Exploitable Result

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

Deliverable 14.1, Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation strategy and Market uptake (initial version), has been created within the context of Task 14.1 of the TERRAVISION project. It provides the Dissemination, Communication and Exploitation plan, which will be used for the purposes of engaging all relevant stakeholders and audiences, as well as a roadmap of application.

In bullet points, the information in this document can be summarized as follows:

- Dissemination, communication and exploitation objectives
- Target audiences
- Visual material
- Key Performance Indicators (KPIs)
- Monitoring and tracking tools for KPIs
- The exploitation and market uptake actions that will be taken to successfully exploit TERRAVISION's EO Mining Platform

ICCS, as the leader of Task 14.1, will support all partners to ensure their contribution to the fulfilment of the project's dissemination and communication

1. Introduction

1.1 Project Introduction

In the context of the digitization and automation of the mining sector, the EU action plan for Critical Raw Materials (CRM) and Strategic Raw Materials (SRM) promotes the use of Earth Observation (satellite observation) and the Copernicus program as valuable tools for the exploration of related resources and for monitoring the environmental impacts throughout the life cycle of mining activities.

Raw materials are of great importance to the EU's digital and green economy, forming an essential foundation of European industry as well as a prerequisite for the European Green Deal.

Monitoring, assessing, and minimizing the negative impacts of mining operations on the environment and biodiversity, as well as implementing mitigation measures covering activities ranging from resource exploration to mine closure, and adaptation measures to promote resilience to the impacts of climate change and the well-being of neighbouring communities, are among the key principles of the EU for sustainable raw materials.

Through the deployment and validation of EO services that will enhance the safety and sustainability of mineral resources and surrounding areas, and accelerate the market uptake of EO technologies in the mining sector, TERRAVISION will advance the application of EO monitoring technologies in the mining industry on a broader scale, both within the EU and beyond.¹

1.2 Purpose of the Deliverable

This report has been created to present the dissemination and communication plan (D&C plan), as well as the exploitation and market uptake strategy. It is an output of T14.1, "Dissemination and Communication Activities" and provides an initial roadmap of how the project's KPI's will be achieved. It plays an important role in giving all partners an idea of what their D&C contribution will be and how will be monitored. This initial plan will be updated through time as needed, in order to maximize results and to accommodate TERRAVISION's needs as they arise.

1.3 Intended Audience

This document is intended to be disseminated to the Consortium of TERRAVISION project, the European Commission (the funding authority), and any other individuals or groups that have

¹ TERRAVISION Grant Agreement 101138643, Description of the Action (Part B), pg 12-14

an interest in the project. After being approved by European Commission, it will be publicly available on the project’s website, as well as on open access platforms.

1.4 Deliverable structure and relation with other work packages/deliverables

D14.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation strategy and Market uptake (initial version) is comprised of 9 chapters and 5 annexes. The first chapter is an introduction to TERRAVISION, outlining its concept, the scope of this deliverable, its target audience and links with other deliverables and tasks. The second chapter summarizes the communication and dissemination strategy, including the approach to be followed, the objectives and the selected key messages per audience. The third chapter presents the project’s identity while the fourth one highlights the most suitable communication channels and tools. Chapter five provides an overview of the Communication and Dissemination Strategy implementation during the project’s implementation. Chapter six presents the strategy on exploitation and marketing update, while chapter seven outlines the strategy for the management of Intellectual Property.

This deliverable is linked closely with all other Tasks in WP14/15/16. Namely: T14/15/16.2 “Exploitation and innovation Management”, T14/15/16.3 “Market Uptake”, T14/15/16.4 “Clustering Activities”, and T14/15/16.5 “Standardization Activities”. All these tasks require effective communication of the project to specific stakeholders and target audiences.

Moreover, it is linked with deliverables 15.1 “Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation strategy and Market uptake (interim version)”, and 16.1 “Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation strategy and Market uptake (final version)”.

In addition to these specific Tasks and Deliverables, the D&C plan is relevant to any project related activity that requires the dissemination and/or communication of the project’s objectives and/or results.

1.5 Key definitions

Communication, Dissemination and Exploitation are three interrelated concepts with major contribution to the success of the project. Since these concepts can be sometimes confused, in this section will be outlined their objectives, the similarities and differences according to the official guidelines provided by the European Commission.

	Communication	Dissemination	Exploitation
	Inform, promote and communicate activities and results	Make knowledge and results publicly available	Make concrete use of results for commercial, societal, and political purposes
For whom	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Citizens ✓ Stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scientists ✓ Industry 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Researchers ✓ Stakeholders

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Media 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Public authorities ✓ Policymakers ✓ Civil society 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Industry & SMEs ✓ Public authorities ✓ Policymakers ✓ Civil society
How	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Having a well-designed strategy ✓ Conveying clear messages ✓ Using the right channels 	Publishing results in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Scientific magazines ✓ Scientific and/or targeted conferences ✓ Databases 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Creating roadmaps, prototypes, software ✓ Sharing knowledge, skills, data
When	From the start until the end of the action	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Anytime, as soon as results become available ✓ Up to four years after the end of the project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Towards the end of the action and beyond, as soon as exploitable results are available ✓ Up to four years after the end of the project
Why	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Engage the stakeholders ✓ Attract the best experts ✓ Raise awareness of how public money is spent ✓ Show the success of European collaboration 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Maximise the impact of the action ✓ Allow other researchers to go a step forward ✓ Contribute to the advancement of world class knowledge ✓ Make scientific results a common good 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Lead to new legislation or recommendations ✓ For the benefit of innovation, the economy and society ✓ Help to tackle a problem and respond to an existing demand

Table 1- The main differences among the concepts of communication, dissemination and exploitation²

² European Research Executive Agency (European Commission) (2023). Communication, dissemination & exploitation what is the difference and why they all matter, <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/58ad3394-0a63-11ee-b12e-01aa75ed71a1/language-en/format-PDF/source-287940279>

2. Communication and Dissemination Plan

2.1 Approach

As defined in the Description of the Action (Part B), in the TERRAVISION Grant Agreement:

Dissemination in TERRAVISION is focused on (a) disclosure of results to specific target audience segments under the protection of the appropriate IPR strategy to maximize result uptake and (b) generating impact within the academia and R&I sectors, measured by publications and other metrics of engagement with these communities. Communication in the project is aimed at describing and conveying key messages and information about TERRAVISION to a multitude of heterogenous audiences, promoting and encouraging two-way exchange. Communication will be oriented towards highlighting the importance of sustainable industries and how European R&I is spearheading climate crisis mitigation efforts. This will be supported by the local focus of the project.³

The dissemination and communication plan is based on Lasswell's model.

The Lasswell model was first introduced in 1948 by Professor Harold Laswell. It became one of the most influential communication models by answering the following five questions⁴:

Image 1-Laswell's model

Following this linear model, the communication manager is able to set the communication goals through identifying the respective key messages, select the channels to be used and the audiences that the project aims to address, design the communication strategy to be

³ TERRAVISION Grant Agreement 101138643, Description of the Action (Part B), pg 28

⁴ <https://helpfulprofessor.com/lasswell-model-of-communication/>

followed and finally identifies the most effective way to maximize its impact towards all target audiences.

While Laswell’s model has been used for the creation of the plan, the implementation of the plan will follow the AIDA⁵(Awareness, Interest, Desire, Action) model.

The AIDA model was first introduced in 1898 by E. St. Elmo Lewis, an American businessman. His objective was the optimization of sales calls, and in specific the way in which the seller and buyer interacted with regards to the product.

Image 2-AIDA model

The phases are as follows:

Awareness/Initial Phase/M1-M9 – During this period efforts are and will be focused on creating awareness for TERRAVISION.

Channels
Website and social media

Interest/1st Intermediate Phase/M10-M18 – During this stage the dissemination of early results will commence to reach the scientific community. Communication of the project will

⁵ <https://en.ryte.com/wiki/AIDA>

continue through existing and new channels. This is the time period when liaison activities will also become an important component.

Channels
Website and social media
Newsletters
Networks
Publications
Conferences

Desire/2nd intermediate Phase/M19-M30 – During this stage attention will be given to furthering engagement with target audiences. The dissemination of scientific results will continue, and target markets will start being informed about the added value of TERRAVISION services. This stage will create the right conditions for the end products of the project to be successfully taken up by the markets.

Channels
Website and social media
Newsletters
Networks
Publications
Conferences

Action/Final Phase/M31-M48 – All efforts of the previous stages culminate into this final stage, which focuses on maximizing the awareness of TERRAVISION within the relevant markets and industries.

Channels
Website and social media
Newsletters
Networks
Publications
Conferences

2.2 Communication and Dissemination Objectives

Through its clear stages and intended output for each one, Laswell’s model helps set clear dissemination and communication objectives for the D&C plan. This is crucial to ensure that there is a clear vision of what the strategy wants to achieve, and to create a realistic roadmap of the D&C actions.

In detail, the objectives of the D&C plan are the following:

Communication Objectives	Dissemination Objectives
Create public awareness about the project, its results, and impacts by reaching identified target groups	Create interest in the scientific community
Make the project a valid source of information	Get stakeholders, who can bring TERRAVISION closer to its market application goals, involved
Facilitate the collaboration between TERRAVISION and other projects/organizations/groups in the field	Increase the impact of project outcomes
	Make the knowledge acquired during the project, and the technologies and methodologies developed, accessible
	Bring forward collaborative activities with other projects/initiatives/organizations

Table 2 – D&C objectives ⁶

2.3 Key Audiences

For the purposes of creating effective, tailored key messages to communicate project objectives and outcomes more efficiently, four main target groups have been identified. In the table below, each target group and its audiences are matched with the communication channels which will be used for the dissemination of key messages. Additionally, the goals of communicating with each group are listed below. These have already been identified in the DoA in the TERRAVISION Grant Agreement.

⁶ TERRAVISION Grant Agreement 101138643, Description of the Action (Part B), pg 28

Target Group	Channels	Goals
<p>TG1- Scientific Community:</p> <p>Universities and research institutes (EO research, Environmental/Data/Material sciences, Physics, Mathematics, Mechanical/Geotechnical Engineering, Digital technologies and process engineering etc.), Projects conducting research in the same fields as TERRAVISION</p>	<p>Website, Conferences/Events, Social Media (LinkedIn, YouTube), Publications, Datasets, Articles</p>	<p>Sharing of knowledge, enrich open-source resources with new results, facilitate inter-disciplinary collaborations</p>
<p>TG2- Industry & Innovators:</p> <p>Business networks; utilities, associations (Euromines, ERMA, ICMM etc.); technology providers; industrial end-users; industrial clusters, Standard development organizations</p>	<p>Website, Press releases, Conferences/Events, Social Media (Twitter, LinkedIn, YouTube), Publications, Datasets, Videos, Articles</p>	<p>Highlight project results, impacts, replication and transferability potential to enhance new industrial performance improvements, sustainability and positive environmental impact to the relevant sectors of the mining industry</p>
<p>TG3-Governmental Organizations:</p> <p>Regulatory bodies; standardization bodies; regional/national administrations, and urban stakeholders; financial institutions (European Central Bank, European Investment Bank, European Bank for Reconstruction and Development, World Bank etc.)</p>	<p>Website, Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter), Publications, Conferences and Events</p>	<p>Added value of TERRAVISION to their sector. Boosting of local economies, increased resilience of critical EU sectors, 2030 policy goals</p>
<p>TG4-Citizens and Society:</p> <p>EU citizens; local communities in mining areas; citizen networks and associations involved in advocating for sustainable mining (ENSQM, IISD, RMF, ARM, Diakonia, ISSA, ISAEI, Women's rights & Mining etc.)</p>	<p>Website, Press Releases, Social Media (LinkedIn, Twitter, YouTube), Videos, Articles</p>	<p>Make the wider public and specific citizen's organizations aware of the project.</p> <p>Show that TERRAVISION can have a positive effect in the EU and local communities.</p>

Table 3-Target Groups⁷

⁷ TERRAVISION Grant Agreement 101138643, Description of the Action (Part B), pg 29

2.4 Key Messages

At the core of each D&C strategy, and next to the identified key audiences, lie the key messages. These are the general messages of the strategy, from which tailored key messages are formed and matched to target audiences.

2.4.1 General Messages

The general message can be defined as follows: Raw materials are central to the European industrial sector, as well as an integral part of the EU digital and green economy, and the European Green Deal. TERRAVISION will create an integrated platform to enhance the critical raw material value chain and help implementing sustainable practices.

2.4.2 Key-words

Key words are a selection of words, relevant to the project, its goals, and its outcomes. Working with these key words as a starting point when communicating a key message increases the chances that the message will: 1) reach its intended audience by increasing message visibility (i.e. through social media); 2) have a higher impact on the audience (through words that are related to the audience's causes); 3) remain within the defined brand of the project.

Some of the key-words that have been selected for TERRAVISION are:

- Sustainable mining
- Raw materials
- Earth Observation
- European Green Deal
- Environmental resilience
- European Industry
- Raw material waste reduction
- Early Hazard Identification
- Biodiversity

2.4.3 Tailored Key Messages

By having the general message and the key words as guides, a number of tailored key messages have been created. In the table below, these messages are matched to the target groups (mentioned in Table 2) to which they are tailored for. More tailored key messages will be added as the project progresses.

For reference: TG1 is the Scientific Community, TG2 is Industry and Innovators, TG3 is Governmental Organizations, and TG4 is Citizens and Society.

These messages were formulated by taking into consideration the expected outcomes of the project, as they have been described in the TERRAVISION Grant Agreement, in chapter 2.2.1 “Scientific, Economic/Technological, Societal Outcomes of TERRAVISION”.⁸

Key Messages	TG1	TG2	TG3	TG4
TERRAVISION will increase operational efficiency by 40%, and reduce losses and overall costs that are linked with operations and environmental assessment, and exploration by 30%		✓	✓	
TERRAVISION will bring added value services which cover the entire value chain of critical raw materials, addressing data heterogeneity limitations		✓		
TERRAVISION will increase knowledge about raw material resources in the EU	✓	✓	✓	✓
TERRAVISION will contribute to the implementation of the EU action plan on Critical Raw Materials	✓	✓	✓	✓
Monitoring of land cover and use will help mining companies better assess the impact on the environment and identify which areas can be conserved and restored			✓	✓
Monitoring of water quality in areas around mining sites will help ensure compliance with regulations and protect natural resources	✓		✓	✓
Monitoring of social impact (changes in population density, land tenure, access to resources) will help inform efforts of engaging the community and identify potential conflicts			✓	✓
TERRAVISION will improve standardization efforts for interoperability of geospatial data and services in the mining industry	✓	✓		
TERRAVISION will develop a robust framework for Analysis Ready Data and create an EO mining services platform	✓	✓	✓	

Table 4-Key messages

⁸ TERRAVISION Grant Agreement 101138643, Description of the Action (Part B), pg 23-26

3. Project Identity and Templates

3.1 Project Identity

The project's identity was based on a creative brief, which outlined the objectives of the project, as well as the characteristics that were deemed important to come out in the design. It was decided that emphasis should be given to two aspects: 1) The Earth Observation, and 2) Environmental resilience. Additionally, it was important for the logo to convey the project's relation to the mining sector.

3.1.1 Logo

Based on the creative brief, the TERRAVISION logo was developed in variations of.

- One color
- Two color
- Horizontal
- Vertical

Examples:

Image 4-Logo 2 colors, vertical, positive

Image 3-Logo 2 colors, vertical, negative

Image 5-Logo horizontal, black and white

3.1.2 Color Palette

Colors for the TERRAVISION visual identity were inspired by the mining area itself. The colors of the earth, of the CRMs, and of the environment surrounding mining sites were the starting points. Shades of green took a central role, being supported by brown/red colors.

Below are some examples of raw materials and landscapes that inspired the color palette.

Image 7-Jade

Image 6-Copper

Image 8-Bauxite mine

Main Colors

CMYK = **C75 M68 Y68 K90**
 RGB = **R9 G82 B74**
 #3b524a

CMYK = **C34 M0 Y31 K0**
 RGB = **R173 G214 B189**
 #abd5bd

Additional Colors

CMYK = **C0 M1 Y0 K0**
 RGB = **R129 G129 B129**
 #808080

CMYK = **C18 M25 Y17 K0**
 RGB = **R188 G113 B117**
 #bc2829

CMYK = **C11 M11 Y10 K0**
 RGB = **R170 G78 B80**
 #ac2626

MAIN and ADDITIONAL COLORS

CMYK colors are used in printing material. RGB colors are used on web applications.

Additional color palette can be used for layouts and artworks such as website/posters/leaflets e.t.c. in case you need a small touch of color contrast. These colors cannot replace main color palette or logotype official colors.

Image 9-TERRAVISION color palette

Image 10-TERRAVISION extra colors

3.1.3 Brand Book

The brand book is essential, as it ensures continuity of the brand identity throughout all communication activities. It provides consortium partners, as well as external partners, with clear guidelines about proper logo usage, brand typography, and brand colors. It is accessible via the consortium repository for the TERRAVISION partners, as well as the project [website](#) for the public.

3.2 Templates

Based on the guidelines provided by the brandbook, a series of templates has been created for the project in MS office. These include:

- A presentation template (MS PowerPoint)
- A deliverables template (MS Word)

These templates are accessible to partners via the project's repository and can be seen in [Annex 1](#).

4. Communication Tools and Actions

4.1 Online Tools

A variety of online tools will be used for TERRAVISION’s communication activities. These include the project website and social media pages.

4.1.1 TERRAVISION Website

The TERRAVISION website, <https://terravision-project.eu/>, is the first point of contact between the project and the public. It was designed following all the necessary guidelines to be in accordance with the brand identity. The website was built using WordPress⁹ and has an easy-to-use interface, showcasing the most important aspects of the project.

On the landing page of the website, the visitor is introduced to the project through the logo, the tagline of the project, as well as a background photo which helps to understand what TERRAVISION is about. Namely, there is two people at an excavation site, pointing forward towards the green planes, symbolizing a vision for a more sustainable mining sector.

Image 11-TERRAVISION home page

⁹ <https://wordpress.org/about/>

Scrolling further down, visitors can get read about the demo sites, where TERRAVISION will test its platform. The demo pages are visually enriched with photos from the mines where the pilot tests will run.

Image 12-TERRAVISION home page-demos

Overview and challenges

TERNAMAG, a subsidiary of the GEC TERNIA GROUP is engaged in mining magnesite on Evia Island, Greece. Presently, they run an underground mine in Gerolimata and an open pit mine in Kalavros, both equipped with beneficiation plants. Their exploration efforts encompass traditional methods like drilling and geological mapping. They also seek to expand operations to new deposits and surrounding areas. Challenges include accurate risk assessment for ground deformations, managing raw material waste (tailing), and handling a considerable waste production from the Gerolimata underground mine and Kalavros open pit mine.

The main motivation for the participation of TERNAMAG is related with the (i) modernization of the exploration activities currently undertaken to expand operations at existing sites and adjacent areas based on EO services, (ii) the urgent need for remote sensing and real-time assessment of dynamic hazards).

Image 13-TERNAMAG pilot site

Moving further down, some important information about the project, as well as participating partners are shown.

Image 14-TERRAVISION home page-info

Finally, the website hosts a number of different menus, namely “Platform” (where the TERRAVISION platform will be available when ready); “About TERRAVISION” which gives information about the project’s scope; “Pilot Sites” which redirects to the demo locations and information about each one; “News and Events” where the news of the project are updated; “Publications” where the public can have access to all disseminated material and the communication kit; and finally “Watch” where the project videos, and interviews will be uploaded.

Image 15-Website Publications/Materials submenu

4.1.1.1 Google Analytics

In order to monitor website traffic and have a picture of visitor profiles and purposes, TERRAVISION is using Google Analytics. Monitoring website visits allows for KPIs to be tracked, and gives valuable information with regards to the audiences (sessions per country, desktop or mobile user, time of visit).

Image 16-Google Analytics- users

Image 17-Google Analytics-user acquisition

Image 19-TERRAVISION LinkedIn page

4.1.2.2 X (Formerly Known as Twitter)

Where LinkedIn is used to reach audiences using long-form posts and tap into the audiences' scientific and business curiosity and interests, X (FKA Twitter) uses small, hashtag rich texts to create short and succinct messages. Through the use of these hashtags, messages can be easily targeted to specific audiences and communities. [TERRAVISION EU Project](#) is the project's X page.

As of June 1st 2024 the page has 2 posts and 21 followers.

Image 20-TERRAVISION X page

4.1.2.5 YouTube

TERRAVISION's YouTube channel will host the project's general video, as well as interviews and other video material that will be created during the project. It will be activated as soon as the project's general video is created (Planned for M7).

4.1.3 TERRAVISION Podcast

A dedicated TERRAVISION podcast series, which will be focused on the developed innovation services will be launched during the project. The series will be launched within the final phase of the project to target business and industry related audiences.

4.2 Dissemination and Communication Tools

4.2.1 Communication Kit

Based on the brand identity of the project, a number of printed material has been designed (poster, roll-up banner, brochure, general presentation). Ad hoc material will be created when and if the need arises.

The communication kit is available to the consortium via the repository and is also available on the project website (<https://terravision-project.eu/publications/materials/>).

Image 21-TERRAVISION roll-up banner (example of material), TERRAVISION brochure (front and back pages)

Image 22-TERRAVISION general presentation (example of material)

4.2.2 Newsletter

A total of 8 digital newsletters will be disseminated throughout the project to TERRAVISION’s internal and external stakeholders, as well as communities that have aligned interests. The circulation of the newsletter will be done using Mailchimp¹⁰, and will also be disseminated through LinkedIn’s newsletter services.

The content of the newsletter will cover recent achievements of the project, as well as major upcoming events to which recipients will be invited.

4.3 Press Activities

A number of press releases and articles (8 each) will be disseminated during the project’s lifetime. These will cover major milestones, such as the Kick-off meeting and Final event, news regarding the Pilot Sites in Greece and Spain, as well as other newsworthy developments related to technologies developed by the TERRAVISION team.

¹⁰ <https://mailchimp.com/>

ICCS will be leading this task, but all partners are expected to contribute by disseminating press releases and articles in their native languages and through local media outlets.

Image 23-TERRAVISION KoM press release-press version

All press releases and articles are available to the public via the TERRAVISION [website](#).

Image 24-KoM press release

4.3.1 Media Channel Selection

Media for the dissemination of press releases and articles will be selected according to the content of the piece and the AIDA phase the project is in.

While in Phases 2 & 3, the focus will be on reaching scientific communities, in Phase 4 the main objective is to reach business and industry communities. Therefore, as the content and target audiences are selected, so will the media.

4.4 General video

Within the project’s lifetime a video will be produced to summarize the project’s concept and objectives. The video will be stored in the official website and on YouTube channel and aims to promote the project through conferences and events.

4.5 Conferences and Events

TERRAVISION’s results and research outputs will be presented in conferences and events, as part of the project’s dissemination activities. All partners will participate in these efforts, and a consolidated plan of conferences and events that will be attended will be prepared, and included into the D&C strategy by the second phase (M10).

In order to gather all necessary information, an “individual D&C plan” form has been given to all partners to fill out.

The image displays two versions of the 'Individual dissemination and communication plans' form, both featuring the TERRA VISION logo at the top left. The forms are divided into several sections:

- Header:** Includes fields for 'PARTNER NAME', 'DATE', and 'CONTACT PERSON'.
- Participation in Events:** A table with columns for 'No.', 'Name of the event (action event)', 'Date (action)', 'Place (action)', and 'What to present'. It includes a sub-header: 'Participation in events (conferences, meetings, online events, exhibitions) Planned activities Period: 2014 - End of the project'.
- Publications:** A table with columns for 'No.', 'Type/genre/category / conference', 'Place (action)', 'Topic planned to be addressed (action)', and 'Other partners to be involved in its delivery (name DNP the organization)'. It includes a sub-header: 'Publications (journal, conference proceedings, magazine) Planned activities Period: 2014 - End of the project'.
- Clustering Activities:** A table with columns for 'No.', 'Name of relevant organization', 'Type of activity', 'Date', and 'Place'. It includes a sub-header: 'Collaboration activities with relevant projects Planned activities Period: 2014 - End of the project'.
- Communication Activities:** A table with columns for 'No.', 'Activity', 'Date', and 'What to present'. It includes a sub-header: 'Webinars, Social Media, e-Newsletters and e-mail Campaigns, Press Releases, Blogs, Podcasts, Meetings Planned activities Period: 2014 - End of the project'.
- Other Comments:** A section with horizontal lines for additional notes.

At the bottom of each form, there is a logo for 'Co-funded by the European Union'.

Image 25-Individual D&C plans form

To help partners with these plans, a Calendar of Events ([Annex 2](#)) with a list of conferences and events will be provided. This is available to the consortium via the repository.

4.5.1 Stakeholders Workshops

Two Stakeholders’ Workshops will take place during the project lifetime to disseminate the project key outcomes and results to the identified stakeholders.

4.5.2 Final Event

A Final Event will be organised by the end of the project to present the project results to all target audiences including stakeholders. The Final Event will feature presentations illustrating the project's progress including demonstrations and videos if available.

4.6 Publications

The project's research will also be published in peer-reviewed journals, and relevant conferences. In the same way that a list of conferences will be available to the consortium, so will be a list of journals that will be updated throughout the project ([Annex 3](#)).

Project partners are advised to publish their research in Open Access journals, and to make use of Open Research Europe, as well as Zenodo¹¹.

TERRAVISION's Zenodo community will be launched in Phase 2 of the project, in accordance with D&C strategy goals.

4.7 Networking and liaison activities

Networking and liaison activities will be mainly performed within T14.4 "Clustering Activities", led by partner ISMC.

Starting in July 2024, ISMC will perform research aiming to:

- review of current and past projects that are relevant to TERRAVISION objectives and activities;
- review of HE and H2020 projects, and other relevant initiatives to gather information on outputs, research results, issues identified, etc.;
- outline policy and market development issues;
- compile a list of organisations and projects to be involved in the two clustering events;
- select most interesting projects and initiatives for direct contact and develop interview and monitoring tools to develop common clustering activities.

In addition, a calendar of events will be identified with stakeholder groups and other initiatives as mentioned in the GA.

4.8 Datasets

During the project's lifetime four datasets will be developed and shared with the public, and mainly in the final two phases of the project.

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/>

5. Implementation of the Communication and Dissemination Plan

5.1 Partners' Input

According to their area of expertise and assigned person months for WP14/15/16, each partner is expected to contribute to D&C efforts in varying degrees.

Partner	PMs in WP14/15/16
ICCS	25
SINTEF	4
CORE	20
AUTH	3
ITA	3
TERRADUE	5
AURORA	4
VITO	0
UNE	14
GEOS	0
DIMAP	0
CANTERAS	3
TERNAMAG	3
THARSIS	3
ISMC	23

Table 5 - WP14/15/16 PMs¹²

¹² TERRAVISION Grant Agreement 101138643, Description of the Action (Part A), pg 35

5.2 KPIs

The TERRAVISION consortium is committed to a set of D&C KPIs, outlined in the GA, which have been chosen to outline clear-cut and easy to visualize goals, in to measure the achievement of the goals of the D&C strategy.

Key Point Indicator	Target Value
Website Visitors	2000
Newsletters	8
Press Releases	8
Conferences/Events	12
LinkedIn Followers	500
X Followers	500
Publications	10
Videos	5
Articles	8
Datasets	4

Table 6-D&C KPIs¹³

¹³ TERRAVISION Grant Agreement 101138643, Description of the Action (Part B), pg 29

5.3 Roadmap and preliminary action plan

A preliminary action plan and roadmap of D&C activities has been put together to serve as a phase by phase guide.

The roadmap provides an overview of the communication activities that will be carried out and will be modified according to any unforeseen needs that might arise.

Phase 1 M1-M9			
Description	D&C Activity	Actions taken	Milestones & Deliverables
This is the “Awareness” phase of the project. Priority will be given to the establishment of the brand identity and set up of the channels which will present the project to the wider audience.	Logo, color palette, brand book, project templates	Ready in M3	D14.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation strategy and Market uptake (initial version)
	Communication material	Roll-up banner M5 Poster M5 General presentation M5 Brochure (project introduction and vision) M6	
	Website	Launched M4 Visitors by M10 >100	
	Social Media (LinkedIn+X)	Launched M3 Followers by M10 >100 each	
	Videos	1 general video by M7	
	Press Releases	1 Press Release M3 (KoM)	
	Newsletters	1 by the end of Phase 1	
Phase 2 M10-M18			

<p>This is the “Interest” phase of the project. While all communication channels will be updated, early results will be disseminated in journals and conferences. This will ensure that the project is reaching out to researchers and scientific communities.</p>	Website maintained	Visitors by M19>500	D14.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation strategy and Market uptake (initial version) M6
	Social media maintained	Followers by M19 >150 each	
	Videos	>2 Pilot Site videos by M19	
	Press Releases	>2 Press Releases	
	Newsletters	2 during phase 2	
	Articles	2 during phase 2	
	Publications	>5 by M19	
	Conferences/Events	>5 by M19	
	Synergies with DIHs	>4 by M19	
	Datasets	>2 by M19	
<p>Phase 3 M19-M30</p>			
<p>This is the “Desire” phase of the project. While all communication channels will be updated, further engagement of target audiences will be pursued. During this phase, evolving research results will continue to be disseminated, while markets will be informed about the added value of TERRAVISION to business and technology.</p>	Website maintained	Visitors by M31>1500	D15.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation strategy and Market uptake (interim version) M24
	Social media maintained	Followers by M31 >400 each	
	Videos	>2 TERRAVISION technological outputs/business applications	
	Press Releases	>2 Press Releases	
	Newsletters	2 during phase 3	
	Articles	2 during phase 3	
	Publications	>5 by M31	
	Conferences/Events	>5 by M31	
Synergies with DIHs	>4 by M31		

	Datasets	>2 by M31	
Phase 4			
M31-M48			
This is the “Action” phase of the project. While all communication channels will be updated, the focus will be directed towards maximizing awareness within target industries about the project’s exploitable results.	Website maintained	Visitors by M48>2000	D16.1 Dissemination and Communication Activities, Exploitation strategy and Market uptake (final version) M48
	Communication material	Brochure to target industries and stakeholders	
	Social media maintained	Followers by M48 >500 each Stakeholders reached in total >10000	
	Press Releases	>3 Press Releases	
	Newsletters	3 during phase 4	
	Articles	2 during phase 4	
	Podcast	The podcast series will be launched in M31 to maximize the reach of business and industry audiences	

Table 7-Roadmap and Action Plan

5.4 Dissemination Procedure

A document outlining the dissemination procedures ([Annex 4](#)) has been created and shared with the project partners, which outlines the steps that should be taken before and after any D&C related activities.

These procedures help ensure that: enough time is given to the consortium to review any research which will be published; partners have relevant information about conference participations to discuss collaborations; the brand identity and EU acknowledgment are correctly followed; material from the actions can be gathered to use for promotion of the project; and activities are properly logged and kept track of.

5.4.1 EU Acknowledgment

All D&C material must display, in a manner that is clear and visible, the following disclaimer and EU emblem.

Image 26 - EU Acknowledgment

Image 27 - Example of EU Acknowledgment placement

5.4.2 Monitoring and recording

All D&C actions will be recorded on the Dissemination Registry document ([Annex 5](#)) of TERRAVISION, which is accessible to the consortium via the repository.

This live document will help to monitor the progress that is made towards reaching the goals that are set within the GA of the project in the form of KPIs.

Every 6 months the KPIs will be updated and modification to the D&C strategy will be made, if needed.

6. Exploitation and market uptake strategy

The “Exploitation and market uptake strategy” section begins with outlining our approach to exploit TERRAVISION’s research results. The strategy is built upon two pillars:

1. **Exploitation activities:** the first pillar begins with an analysis of the project’s KERs, exploring relevant IPR protection mechanisms and market exploitability. Moreover, it includes analyses on customer profiles, value propositions, and exploitation routes. Finally, by assessing innovation potential and designing sustainable business models, the project aims to drive impactful innovations aligned with industry needs.
2. **Market Uptake activities:** the second pillar includes assessing market barriers, conducting market analysis, and integrating a competition analysis within a Porter 5-Forces framework. Through understanding market dynamics and competitiveness, the strategy aims to ensure that TERRAVISION results will be widely adopted by the mining industry.

Furthermore, the strategy for IP management is introduced, aiming to foster collaboration while safeguarding innovation. In the next steps, an analysis of various IPR protection mechanisms will take place to ensure successful post-project commercialization of project results.

Finally, a report detailing the first examination of TERRAVISION's Key Exploitable Results (KERs) is provided, based on an exploitation workshop organised in Month 4 (April 2024). Five KERs were identified and validated by partners: **(a)** TERRAVISION Platform, **(b)** Data Ecosystem for Large-scale Earth Observation (EO) mining services, **(c)** Analysis Ready Data (ARD) and Raw spectral signatures, **(d)** Earth Observation (EO) services for the mining industry, and **(e)** Green and Resilience Accountability component.

The TERRAVISION Exploitation Strategy aims to identify the project’s individual and joint exploitable results, and analyses their exploitation routes, which could focus on commercial exploitation, standardization, or further research activities. CORE leads the “Exploitation and Innovation Management” task, based on TERRAVISION’s KERs. IPR protection considerations, customer profile, value proposition design, exploitation routes, innovation potential and sustainable business models are the key activities that will be carried out, and are presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1 TERRAVISION Exploitation Activities

Figure 2 presents the TERRAVISION market uptake activities that will focus on analysing internal and external market barriers, developing roadmaps for commercializing KERs, and conducting competition and SWOT analyses to understand TERRAVISION's market dynamics and competitiveness.

Figure 2 TERRAVISION Market Uptake Activities

6.1 Plan for exploitation and market uptake activities

TERRAVISION's Exploitation Plan is structured across three phases, illustrated in Figure 3. Over the initial phase (M1-M18), the primary focus involves analyzing TERRAVISION KERs, defining strategies for protecting IPRs and evaluating their market potential, exploitability and future impact to industry. In the mid phase (M19-M36), the emphasis shifts towards understanding TERRAVISION's target customers' needs, serving as the foundation for crafting the TERRAVISION value proposition. Concurrently, exploitation routes strategies for TERRAVISION KERs will be developed. In the last phase (M37-M48), the focus will centre on examining TERRAVISION's innovation potential and formulating sustainable business models.

Figure 3 Key phases for developing the TERRAVISION exploitation plan

Similarly, TERRAVISION's market uptake strategy is divided into three phases as visualized in Figure 4. During the initial period (M1-M18), an analysis of market barriers will take place, with strategies for mitigation developed through literature reviews and validation by stakeholders. In the mid phase (M19-M36), feedback from sister projects will provide an external view giving the consortium a comprehensive understanding. Moreover, a market analysis will assess market size, outlook, and dynamics to identify key geographical markets for TERRAVISION's post-project commercialization. Additionally, a SWOT analysis will be conducted. In the final phase (M37-M48), the roadmap to achieve TRL-9 for TERRAVISION's KERs will be developed, analyzing partners' roles, key activities, and milestones. This will be complemented by an analysis of the TERRAVISION competition.

Figure 4 Key phases for developing the TERRAVISION market uptake plan

As described, TERRAVISION's Plan for Exploitation and Market Uptake is structured into three phases, aligned with each work package (WP14, WP15, and WP16). Each phase is organized with specific subtasks and timelines, as outlined below.

WP14 “Synergies, Awareness and Market Uptake” (M1 - M18)

T14.2: “Exploitation and Innovation management”

- **Analysis of KERs:** Defining and analyzing project’s KERs marks the initial activity, clarifying their potential for exploitation to inform strategic decisions and resource allocation, ultimately optimizing project outcomes.
- **Analysis of IPR mechanisms:** The analysis will focus on safeguarding IPRs and outlines the strategies employed to protect the project's KERs.
- **Market Potential, Exploitability and Impact to Industry:** It will assess how each project’s KER can drive innovation, meet market needs, and achieve industry transformation.

T14.3: Market uptake

- **Internal Market Barriers Analysis:** It will assess deployment barriers from the supply side and adoption barriers from the demand side, alongside mitigation strategies for them. The analysis of the market barriers will be based on a 2-step process: (1) literature search of market barriers, (2) validation from both the technology providers and the End-Users.

The projected timeframe for these activities is depicted in Figure 5.

TERRAVISION Plan for exploitation and market uptake activities	2024												2025											
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16	17	18						
	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun	Jul	Aug	Sep	Oct	Nov	Dec	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	May	Jun						
WP14 Synergies, Awareness and Market Uptake (M1 - M18)						D14.1												RVI						
T14.2 Exploitation and Innovation Management																								
T14.2.1 Analysis of KERs																								
T14.2.2 Analysis of IPR Mechanisms																								
T14.2.3 Analysis of Market Potential, Exploitability, and Impact to Industry																								
T14.3 Market Uptake																								
T14.3.1 Internal Market Barriers Analysis																								

Figure 5 TERRAVISION's “Plan for exploitation and market uptake activities” for WP14 (M1-M18)

WP15 “Synergies, Awareness and Market Uptake” (M19 – M36)

T15.2: “Exploitation and Innovation management”

- **Customer Profile:** We will analyze challenges & risks that customer encounter (Customer Pains), and uncovering their needs, desires, and delightful surprises (Customer Gains).
- **Value Proposition:** We will analyze how customer challenges and risks can be addressed (Pain Relievers) and benefits and value can be delivered (Gain Creators).
- **Exploitation Routes:** Exploitation routes for each KER will be selected, either direct or indirect, aiming to maximize technology exploitation and project benefits.

T15.3: Market uptake

- **External View of Market Barriers:** To gain an outside perspective on market barriers, we will get feedback from our sister projects and other H2020/Horizon Europe mining projects.

- **Market Analysis:** We will conduct a thorough examination of the market, analyzing its size, trends, and dynamics to pinpoint key geographical markets for TERRAVISION's commercialization efforts.

- **SWOT Analysis:** We will conduct an analysis to gain insights into TERRAVISION's internal and external factors essential for strategic planning and competitive positioning.

The projected timeframe for these activities is depicted in Figure 6.

Figure 6 TERRAVISION’s “Plan for exploitation and market uptake activities” for WP15 (M19-M36)

WP16 “Synergies, Awareness and Market Uptake” (M37 – M48)

T16.2: “Exploitation and Innovation management”

- **Innovation Potential:** The goal will be to assess KERs in terms of their market potential, innovation readiness and innovation management, using the JRC’s Innovation Radar methodology as a guide.

- **Sustainable business models:** We will employ the “Triple Layer Business Model Canvas” (Joyce & Paquin, 2016), integrating economic, environmental, and social value creation to advance the market readiness of KERs.

T16.3: Market Uptake

- **Competition analysis:** An assessment will be conducted to evaluate similar offerings in the market, which will be integrated into a Porter 5-Forces analysis, shedding light on the industry's competitiveness.

- **Partners’ roles and Milestones:** For TERRAVISION’s KERs aiming for commercial use, we will develop the roadmap to reach TRL-9, analysing the role of the partners, the key activities (technical and commercial), and milestones.

The projected timeframe for these activities is depicted in Figure 7.

Figure 7 TERRAVISION’s “Plan for exploitation and market uptake activities” for WP16 (M37-M48)

7. Strategy for the Management of Intellectual Property

Securing our project's intellectual property is essential for maintain a competitive advantage, prevent unauthorized use, and manage the dissemination of our innovations effectively. Selecting the appropriate IPR protection mechanisms can help keep competitors out of our market and facilitate seamless collaboration with external organizations (Grimaldi et al., 2021). Additionally, they offer different ways to maximize KERs value and revenue.

Our project's IP Management strategy aims promote collaboration while ensuring our innovations can spread beyond the project's boundaries. Additionally, following IPR rules also helps avoid clashes with our partners over ownership. As a result, we aim for an **"open as possible, closed as necessary"** approach, sharing information openly but imposing reasonable limits when needed, based on democratic reasons (McJohn, 2021). Following this approach, safeguarding knowledge is crucial for achieving the European Union's policy objectives, including strategic autonomy and promoting green and digital transitions. (European Commission, 2022).

Mechanisms	Description
Patent	A patent is an exclusive right granted for an invention a product or a process that provides a new way of doing something, or that offers a new technical solution to a problem. A patent provides patent owners with protection for their inventions. Protection is granted for a limited period, generally 20 years.
Utility models	Utility models are similar to patents as a protection method by granting a limited exclusive right. They are usually cheaper to obtain, have a shorter term (around 10 years), and have less stringent patentability requirements. They are well suited for protecting inventions that make small adaptations or improvements to existing products.
Industrial Design	An Industrial Design refers to the ornamental or aesthetic aspects of an article. A design may consist of three-dimensional features, such as the shape or surface of an article, or two-dimensional features such as patterns, lines, or colour.
Trademark	A trademark is a distinctive sign that identifies certain goods or services produced or provided by an individual or a company. The system helps consumers to identify and purchase a product or service based on whether its specific characteristics and quality as indicated by its unique trademark meet their needs.
Copyright	Copyright is a legal term used to describe the rights that creators have over their literary and artistic works. Works covered by copyright range from books, music, paintings, sculpture, and films, to computer programs, databases, advertisements, maps and technical drawings
Trade secrets	Trade secrets are IP rights on confidential information which may be sold or licensed. The unauthorized acquisition, use or disclosure of such secret information in a manner contrary to honest commercial practices by others is regarded as an unfair practice and a violation of trade secret protection.
NDA	A non-disclosure agreement (NDA) is a legally binding contract that establishes a confidential relationship. The party or parties signing the agreement agree that sensitive information they may obtain will not be made available to any others. An NDA may also be referred to as a confidentiality agreement.

Table 8-IPR protection mechanisms methods (MASTERMINE [GA n. 101086497] – Initial DECP, 2023)

In the coming months, we will be examining various IPR strategies (Table 3) that partners in the consortium may use to assess their suitability and effectiveness for each KER. The

European Patent Office includes a [detailed online overview](#) of the IPR protection mechanisms. Examining these protection methods will offer valuable insights into their strengths, weaknesses, and the opportunities and threats they present. By identifying best practices and areas needing improvement, we can refine our approach to safeguarding intellectual property within the TERRAVISION project. This will enhance the integrity and value of our intellectual assets, ultimately helping us navigate the project lifecycle and beyond, ensuring successful commercialization of our results.

7.1 TERRAVISION Key Exploitable Results

As earlier described, an initial identification of KERs is reported in GA. To advance this draft Exploitation Plan, CORE, as a first step, conducted an Exploitation Workshop during M4 and introduced the full definition of Key Exploitable Results [as described by IPR Helpdesk](#):

Key Exploitable Result: “An identified main interesting result, which has been selected and prioritized due to its high potential to be “exploited” – meaning to make use and derive benefits- downstream the value chain of a product, process or solution, or act as an important input to policy, further research, or education.”

This definition was introduced to assist participants understand the concept of exploitation and start developing ideas on exploitation options of their results. This workshop was mainly targeting technology providers, requesting them validate existing list of KERs, provide a full description, define the type of their results (software, hardware, tool, model, methodology, report), the exploitation option (spin-off/startup, academic paper/report, demonstration, further research, social activity, policy recommendation), IPR considerations (patent, copyright, trademark, NDA, trade secret, license), the target market, and the added value this result gives to end users. The exploitable results listed in the GA have been validated by partners and further refined by CORE following the workshop outcomes:

7.1.1 TERRAVISION Platform

The TERRAVISION platform is designed to integrate Earth Observation (EO) data from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem with in-situ technologies, leveraging advanced machine learning and data analysis capabilities. The objective of this KER is to offer novel services for the critical raw materials value chain, enhancing knowledge on resource availability, assessing geo-hazards, and providing sustainability and resilience indices to assess social, environmental and economic performances of mining industry.

The TERRAVISION platform consists of the EO mining services platform (developed by ICCS) and the dashboard visualizations that will include prognostic features (developed by CORE). It will be exploited by commercialising the integrated EO Mining Services Platform as a one-stop solution for sustainable mining practices. The main types of target customers include mining companies, raw materials processors, national and European governmental institutions, and environmental organisations. The envisaged exploitation routes include building strategic partnerships, showcasing effectiveness through pilot demonstrations, and offering various service packages to meet the needs of the mining sector, emphasizing environmental protection, supply chain resilience, and risk management.

7.1.2 Data Ecosystem for Large scale Earth Observation (EO) mining services

The data ecosystem is compiled by various datasets over the different demonstrators and mining sites with a range of sensor sets (i.e. hyperspectral, Lidar, multispectral, cameras) platforms and setups. This will work as an online map that will zonate the area of interest in zones depicting the spatial distribution of hazard against slope instabilities. It will be mainly used by mining companies, unlocking the benefit of comprehensive data integration for monitoring the raw materials life cycle. During the project, AURORA and DIMAP will primarily utilize this. After the project concludes, this KER will serve as a foundation for ongoing research and may be considered for future patenting.

7.1.3 Analysis Ready Data (ARD) and Raw spectral signatures

The primary goal is to develop a Machine Learning framework and algorithms, aimed at improving the spatial resolution of multispectral and hyperspectral spaceborne data. This enhancement will go beyond the capabilities of the original systems and facilitate the cross-platform utilization of SENTINEL, EnMAP, and PRISMA satellites. The framework will leverage the inherent characteristics of spaceborne data and employ super resolution modelling, including Deep Neural Network architectures, to enhance the spatial details of observed properties. Specifically, the aim is to increase the spatial resolution of finer bands (e.g., from 20m and 60m to 10m), while maintaining the spectral resolution integrity. Super resolution and pansharpening techniques will be also applied to EnMAP and PRISMA hyperspectral images to sharpen their spatial resolution using similar spectral resolution but high spatial resolution images from drones or panchromatic images. This will occur by expanding hyperspectral database and automated analysis (grade estimation) for mining and exploration applications, upscaling the process to airborne and satellite hyperspectral data.

ARD will be exploited by ICCS and GEOS as part of the TERRAVISION Platform and will be used as material for further research. This software tool could be potentially licensed to mining companies aiming to offer a user-friendly and customizable ARD processing framework.

7.1.4 Earth Observation (EO) services for the mining industry

EO Services will be developed by ICCS and AUTH as an online software tool for the exploration of raw materials using satellite data. Mineral exploration will be performed by EO.Lab with spaceborne and airborne hyperspectral, generating multispectral and geophysical data both on a local and regional level.

EO.Lab is contributing to the project by focusing primarily on the monitoring of surface motion based on advanced Synthetic Aperture Radar (SAR) interferometric techniques. EO.Lab will contribute to this KER with an operational EO-based monitoring service named SNAPPING. ICCS and AUTH plan to exploit EO services initially for further research and finally as a software tool targeting mining companies that aim to benefit from EO data via a comprehensive suite of EO services for monitoring, exploitation, and risk management. Post-project and before licensing this software tool, it is envisaged that this KER will be patented to secure its IPRs.

7.1.5 Green And Resilience Accountability component

The Green and Resilience Accountability component as a component of the TERRAVISION Platform will be responsible for: **(a)** integrating satellite data with field data which will be processed to assess the environmental impacts of mining industry, **(b)** offering socio-economic metrics related with activities of the mining sector, **(c)** generating dashboard visualizations with prognostic features, and **(d)** implementing resilience and sustainability indices to provide the mining sector with key information about response capabilities to perturbations and shocks but also to assess environmental performance. This component will be jointly produced by ITA, CORE, SINTEF and VITO.

8. Conclusion

The document presented is an initial plan for the Dissemination, Communication, Exploitation and Market uptake of TERRAVISION and its results.

It presents the scope of the strategy that was formulated in the first months of the project to serve as a guide for maximizing awareness and engagement. It is a dynamic document which will be modified and enriched throughout the project and will be adapted as necessary.

TERRAVISION is an ambitious project, spanning over 48 months, with a vision to not only enrich existing scientific knowledge, but also to produce usable results with real impact on CRM management and the Mining Industry.

Therefore, it is important for all identified target audiences to become aware and engaged during the project's lifetime; something which this strategy aims to contribute towards.

Disclaimers of Warranty

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This deliverable has used a standard methodology already developed in CiROCCO project (Grant Agreement number: 101086497), following EU recommendations. Ad hoc modifications were added to comply with the Grant Agreement conditions for TERRAVISION (Grant Agreement number: 101138643).

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TERRAVISION [GA n. 101138643] – (January 2024)

Annexes

Annex 1

Integrated Earth Observation Based Platform, for Novel Services to Enhance the Mining Life Cycle of Critical Raw Materials

DX.X
Deliverable Name

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Consortium

1	Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICS)
2	SINTEF AS (SINTEF)
3	ΕΘΡΕ ΚΕΝΤΡΟ ΚΑΙΝΟΤΟΜΙΑΣ ΜΑΥΣ (CORE)
4	ΑΡΙΣΤΟΤΕΛΕΙΟ ΠΑΝΕΠΙΣΤΗΜΙΟ ΘΕΣΣΑΛΟΝΙΚΗΣ (AUTH)
5	ISTITUTO TECNOLOGICO DE ARAGON (ITA)
6	TERRACUE SRL (TERRACUE)
7	AURORASÉ E.E. (AURORA)
8	VLAAMSE INSTELLING VOOR TECHNOLOGIEÏ ONDERZOEK N.V. (VITO)
9	ASOCIACION ESPAÑOLA DE NORMALIZACION (UNE)
10	S.S.O.S. INGENIERGEGESellschaft MBH (ISEOS)
11	DIMAP-SPECTRAL GMBH (DIMAP)
12	CANTERAS INDUSTRIAL ES SL (CANTERA)
13	ΤΕΡΝΑ ΛΕΥΚΟΘΩΔΙ ΑΝΩΝΥΜΗ ΜΕΤΑΛΛΕΥΤΙΚΗ ΕΜΠΟΡΙΚΗ ΤΕΧΝΙΚΗ ΜΟΝΟΚΑΝΟΝΙΚΗ ΕΤΑΙΡΕΙΑ (ΤΕΡΝΑΜΑ)
14	THYSSIS MINING SOCIEDAD LIMITADA (THYSSIS)
15	CLUSTER PARA LA MINERIA SOSTENIBLE Y SERVICIOS ASOCIADOS DE LA PENINSULA IBERICA-IBERIAN SUSTAINABLE MINING CLUSTER (SMC)

Dissemination level	Choose an item
Type of deliverable	Choose an item
Work package	
Deliverable number, title	
Status - version, date	VO.1, 06/09/2024
Deliverable leader	
Contributing partners	
Contractual date of delivery	
Keywords	

Image 28-TERRAVISION MS Word template

Presentation title

Presenter / Organisation

WPX - Name of WP

Partner Logo

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Annex 2

Calendar of Events				
Date	Event	Location	Website	Important Dates
2024				
09-11 September	SCORP 2024	Hasselt, Belgium	https://www.cheminfo.be/cheminfo-site/2024-2024/scorp-2024/	March 09 Information for exhibitors
24-26 September	INTACED	Duisburg, Germany	https://www.intacced.de/en/welcome-to-intacced	https://www.intacced.de/en/welcome-to-intacced Abstract submission closure 31 March 2024 Notification of acceptance June 2024
23-26 September	IC for ADSC	Rome, Italy	https://www.icsymposiums.com/2024/09/23-26/	Issue of Preliminary Programme: June 2024 Registration Opening: June 2024

Image 30-Calendar of Events

Dissemination Procedures

DESCRIPTION AND PURPOSE

During the project's lifecycle and for a period of 1 year after the end of the project, the dissemination of results by one or several partners, including but not restricted to publications and presentations, shall be governed by the procedure of Article 17.4, Communication, Dissemination, Open Science and Visibility of the Grant Agreement and its Annex 5, Section Dissemination.

The dissemination procedure is to be followed by all partners equally to:

- Produce high quality TERRAVISION publications and presentations;
- Avoid overlaps and possible disclosure of restricted or confidential information;
- Efficiently monitor, record and promote the dissemination activities of the project;
- Secure the brand identity of the project and the EC rules to be followed.

The WP14 leader (CORE) and the T14.1 leader (ICCS) are responsible for ensuring compliance with the procedures. All partners are called to contribute efficiently on the dissemination of the project.

Step by Step Procedure – Conferences and Events

For project presentations and overall participation in conferences or events, partners should notify via email the Project Coordinator (Valantis Tsiakos: valantis.tsiakos@iccs.gr, and T14.1 Leader Katerina Zouroufidou: kate.zouroufidou@iccs.gr) at least 20 days before the dissemination activity (according to the Consortium Agreement, Dissemination Article 8.4, p 19). Any objection by other partners regarding the planned participation should be given within 15 days of receiving notification.

To ensure the visibility of participation in conferences and events partners should consider the following:

Before the event:

- Use the [Dissemination Monitoring Tool](#) to log information about the event
- Send details about the event participation so it can be recorded and disseminated via the project's social media and website.
- Use the appropriate template, logos, EU-funded disclaimer and follow other guidelines presented in this document.

During the event:

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Image 32-Dissemination Procedures

